

Acid catalyzed conversions of taxoids[†]

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Treatment of 10-deacetylbaccatin-III and baccatin-III with dilute HCl affords 10-deacetylbaccatin-V and baccatin-V, respectively. 10-Deacetylbaccatin-V is also obtained when 10-deacetylbaccatin-III is treated with ZnCl₂ or ZnBr₂ in MeOH. These two Lewis acids convert baccatin-III to 10-deacetylbaccatin-III as well 10-deacetylbaccatin-V. BF₃·OEt₂ in CH₂Cl₂ opens the oxetane ring of 7,13-diacetylbaccatin-III to form two regioisomeric products while BBr₃ in the same solvent leads to the contraction of its A-ring along with the oxetane cleavage. CF₃COOH contracts the A-ring of 7-acetylbaccatin-III and 7,13-diacetylbaccatin-III.

Taxol (**1**)¹, one of most promising natural anticancer agent, was originally isolated from *Taxus brevifolia* Nutt. (Taxaceae). The compound possesses a unique diterpenoid structure having an unusual oxetane ring. It exhibits a broad spectrum of anticancer activity and has been approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), US for treatment of refractory advanced ovarian cancer and breast cancer in 1992 and 1994, respectively². Taxol (**1**) belongs to a new series of antimetabolic agent – it acts in an unusual way, binding to polymerized tubulin and stabilizing it to disassembly, thus disrupting the tubulin-microtubule equilibrium and consequently inhibiting mitosis^{3,4}. However, taxol (**1**) is obtained from nature in very low yield and it is highly toxic. Its solubility in aqueous media is also very poor⁵.

During our search for taxol and related taxoids in the Himalayan yew, *Taxus baccata* Linn. (Taxaceae), we have observed⁶⁻⁹ that the regenerable needles of the plant contain 10-deacetylbaccatin-III (**2**), a precursor of taxol, in larger quantity. This compound on suitable modifications can be utilized for semisynthesis of taxol and its different improved derivatives. Here we describe some acid catalyzed conversions of 10-deacetylbaccatin-III (**2**) and its natural and synthetic analogs to generate novel synthetic precursors of taxol related compounds.

10-Deacetylbaccatin-III (**2**) on treatment with dilute HCl underwent epimerization at C-7 to produce 10-deacetylbaccatin-V (**3**)¹⁰ which is also a naturally occurring taxoid.

Similar transformation was also observed when the former was treated with mild Lewis acid ZnBr₂ or ZnCl₂ in MeOH. The mechanism of such epimerization possibly involves¹¹ a retroaldol reaction followed by recyclization to the ther-

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modynamically more stable form with the α -hydroxyl group at C-7. Baccatin-III (4), another natural taxoid also afforded the C-7 epimeric product, baccatin-V (5)¹² on treatment with dilute HCl. The former was also treated with the Lewis acids, ZnBr₂ and ZnCl₂ in MeOH. Two similar products, 10-deacetylbaccatin-III (2) and 10-deacetylbaccatin-V (3) were obtained in each case. The first product was produced by selective deacetylation at C-10 and the second product which was the major product formed through epimerization at C-7 of the first product. Such conversion was previously noted^{11,13} with taxol (1) itself.

9 R = H, R¹ = Ac
10 R = Ac, R¹ = H

12 R = Ac
13 R = H

When 10-deacetylbaccatin-III (2) or baccatin-III (4) was treated with BF₃·OEt₂ in CH₂Cl₂, a complex mixture of products were obtained. To avoid epimerization 7,13-diacetylbaccatin-III (6) which could easily be prepared from 2 or 4 following the reported method¹⁴ was selected. BF₃·OEt₂ opened the oxetane ring of 6 to form two regioisomeric products 7 and 8 whose structures were clearly settled from their ¹H NMR data. In 7, H-5 appeared at δ 3.94 (1H, br s) and H₂-20 at δ 4.20 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz) and 4.05 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz), while in 8 these protons resonated at δ 5.12 (1H, m) and 3.53 (2H, dd, *J* 11.0 and 4.0 Hz), respectively. Compounds 7 and 8 were formed¹³ through the complexation of BF₃·OEt₂ with the oxetane oxygen of 6 followed by participation of the neighbouring C-4 acetoxy group. The A-ring was found to be intact in both the products 7 and 8. However, when BBr₃ was used as Lewis acid taxoid 6 produced two different products 9 and 10 where A-ring was contracted to a 5-membered ring followed by dehydration along with the cleavage of the oxetane ring. The

structures of 9 and 10 were established from the long-range COSY spectrum. Two vinyl protons of both these products showed a long-range coupling to a vinyl methyl group as well as a correlation with C-1 but not with C-11 (HMBC experiment) indicating the proposed 5-membered A-ring in these two compounds. The ¹H NMR spectral data of the protons of the open oxetane portion were compared to those of the corresponding protons of 7 and 8.

7,13-Diacetylbaccatin-III (6) and 7-acetylbaccatin-III (11) were separately treated with CF₃COOH. In the isolated products (12 and 13, respectively) the oxetane ring was found to be intact but the A-ring was contracted to a 5-membered ring though dehydration was not found. It is worthwhile to mention here that different naturally occurring taxoids with such 5-membered A-ring have recently been reported¹⁵. In the HMBC spectra of 12 and 13 C-1 showed a correlation with H₃-16 and H₃-17 but C-11 did not show any correlation with these protons. Some minor products could not be purified from the complex mixture in both the reactions of 6 and 11 with CF₃COOH.

In summary, we have mentioned here the conversions of some natural and synthetic taxoids catalyzed by protonic and Lewis acids. Different types of products involving epimerization, opening of the oxetane ring and the rearrangement of the A-ring have been observed. These products can be utilized as the synthetic precursors for the preparation of various taxol analogs to generate more potent and less toxic anticancer compounds.

Experimental

M.p.s. were measured in a Buchi-510 instrument and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with Varian Gemini 200 MHz and Jeol 500 MHz spectrometers and FABMS with VG-Autospec M. Column chromatography was performed with silica gel (BDH; 100–200 mesh) and TLC with silica gel GF 254. The TLC spots were detected in an iodine chamber and under UV-lamp. The spots were also visualized by spraying the TLC plates with 10% methanolic H₂SO₄ and subsequently heating in an oven.

Treatment of 10-deacetylbaccatin-III and baccatin-III with dilute HCl: To a solution of 10-deacetylbaccatin-III (2) (100 mg) in a mixture of CH₂Cl₂-MeOH (1 : 1; 10 ml) a drop of 1 *N* aqueous HCl was added. The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature, concentrated and purified by column chromatography to obtain 10-deacetylbaccatin-V (3) (62 mg) as a viscous mass and the unchanged 2 (18 mg).

Baccatin-III (4; 100 mg) dissolved in CH₂Cl₂-MeOH (1 : 1; 10 ml) was similarly treated with 1 *N* aqueous HCl

to give baccatin-V (**5**; 66 mg), m.p. 253–254° (MeOH) together with unchanged **4** (15 mg).

Reaction of 10-deacetyl-baccatin-III and baccatin-III with ZnCl₂ and ZnBr₂: To a solution of 10-deacetyl-baccatin-III (**2**; 100 mg) in MeOH (20 ml) anhydrous ZnCl₂ (1 g) was added. The mixture was stirred for 2 days at room temperature. The solvent was removed and the residue taken up in EtOAc (20 ml) and washed with water (2 × 20 ml) and brine (2 × 20 ml). The organic phase was concentrated and the viscous mass was purified by chromatography to produce 10-deacetyl-baccatin-V (**5**; 48 mg) along with unreacted **2** (14 mg).

The reaction of 10-deacetyl-baccatin-III (**2**; 100 mg) with ZnBr₂ (1 g) in MeOH (20 ml) was carried out to afford 10-deacetyl-baccatin-V (**5**; 42 mg) and the unchanged **2** (22 mg).

Baccatin-III (**4**; 100 mg) dissolved in MeOH (20 ml) was treated with ZnCl₂ (1 g) following the above mentioned method to produce 10-deacetyl-baccatin-III (**2**; 15 mg), m.p. 244–245° (MeOH), 10-deacetyl-baccatin-V (**3**; 46 mg) and the unreacted **4** (8 mg).

The reaction of baccatin-III (**4**; 100 mg) with ZnBr₂ (1 g) was carried out in MeOH (20 ml) analogously to produce 10-deacetyl-baccatin-III (**2**; 14 mg) and 10-deacetyl-baccatin-V (**3**; 37 mg) along with unchanged **4** (12 mg).

Reaction of 7,13-diacetyl-baccatin-III with BF₃.OEt₂: 7,13-Diacetyl-baccatin-III (**6**; 100 mg) was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (10 ml), cooled to 0° and stirred under N₂ atmosphere. BF₃.OEt₂ (1 ml dissolved in 5 ml CH₂Cl₂) was added dropwise and the reaction was kept for 2 h. Standard workup yielded an oily mass which was subjected to column chromatography to obtain **7** (31 mg) and **8** (29 mg).

Compound 7: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.04–8.02 (2H, m, ArH), 7.62–7.55 (3H, m, ArH), 6.41 (1H, s, H-10), 6.14 (1H, m, H-13), 5.68 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-2), 5.47 (1H, dd, *J* 11.0, 4.0 Hz, H-7), 4.20 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-20), 4.05 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-20), 3.94 (1H, m H-5), 3.75 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-3), 2.21, 2.20, 2.18 (3H each, s, 3 × OAc), 2.01 (3H, s, Me-18), 1.68 (3H, s, OAc), 1.56, 1.11 and 1.02 (3H each, s, Me-19, Me-17 and Me-16, respectively); FABMS *m/z* 698 (M + H)⁺ (Found: C, 60.75; H, 6.41. C₃₅H₄₄O₁₄ requires: C, 61.05; H, 6.39%).

Compound 8: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.05–8.02 (2H, m, ArH), 7.67–7.48 (3H, m, ArH), 6.38 (1H, s, H-10), 6.07 (1H, m, H-13), 5.66 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-2), 5.41 (1H, dd, *J* 11.0, 4.0 Hz, H-7), 5.12 (1H, m, H-5), 3.74 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-3), 3.53 (2H, dd, *J* 11.0, 4.0 Hz, H₂-20), 2.22, 2.21, 2.17 (3H each, s, 3 × OAc), 2.02 (3H, s, Me-18), 1.71 (3H, s, OAc), 1.54, 1.11, 1.01 (3H each, s, Me-19, Me-17 and Me-16, respectively); FABMS *m/z* 689 (M + H)⁺ (Found:

C, 61.25; H, 6.42. C₃₅H₄₄O₁₄ requires: C, 61.05; H, 6.39%).

Reaction of 7,13-diacetyl-baccatin-III with BBr₃: 7,13-Diacetyl-baccatin-III (**6**; 100 mg) dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (10 ml) was cooled to 0° and stirred under N₂ atmosphere. BBr₃ (1 ml dissolved in 5 ml CH₂Cl₂) was added dropwise and the mixture was kept for 2 h. After standard work up the reaction mixture was purified by column chromatography to produce **9** (17 mg) and **10** (42 mg).

Compound 9: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.03–8.00 (2H, m, ArH), 7.60–7.48 (3H, m, ArH), 6.40 (1H, s, H-10), 5.67 (1H, m, H-13), 5.62 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-2), 5.48 (1H, dd, *J* 11.0, 4.0 Hz, H-7), 4.72, 4.65 (1H each, br s, H₂-16), 4.20 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-20), 4.07 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-20), 3.95 (1H, br s, H-5), 3.74 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-3), 2.20, 2.18, 2.17 (3H each, s, 3 × OAc), 1.94 (3H, s, Me-18), 1.70 (3H, s, OAc), 1.62 (3H, s, Me-16); FABMS *m/z* 671 (M + H)⁺ (Found: C, 62.82; H, 6.32. C₃₅H₄₂O₁₃ requires: C, 62.69, H, 6.27%).

Compound 10: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.02–8.00 (2H, m, ArH), 7.62–7.54 (3H, m, ArH), 6.42 (1H, s, H-10), 5.65 (1H, m, H-13), 5.63 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-2), 5.46 (1H, dd, *J* 11.0, 4.0 Hz, H-7), 5.07 (1H, m, H-5), 4.72, 4.66 (1H each, br s, H₂-16), 3.72 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-3), 2.22, 2.21, 2.18 (3H each, s, 3 × OAc), 1.95 (3H, s, Me-18), 1.70 (3H, s, OAc), 1.61 (3H, s, Me-16); FABMS *m/z* 671 (M + H)⁺ (Found: C, 62.54; H, 6.22. C₃₅H₄₂O₁₃ requires: C, 62.69; H, 6.27%).

Reaction of 7,13-diacetyl-baccatin-III and 7-acetyl-baccatin-III with CF₃COOH: To a solution of 7,13-diacetyl-baccatin-III (**6**; 100 mg) in toluene (5 ml), CF₃COOH (0.1 ml) and water (0.2 ml) were added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and washed with water (3 × 10 ml). The concentrated residue was purified by column chromatography to give **12** (47 mg) and the unreacted **6** (22 mg). Some reaction products could not be purified.

Compound 12: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.03–8.01 (2H, M, ArH), 7.64–7.49 (3H, m, ArH), 6.23 (1H, s, H-10), 5.58 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-2), 5.54 (1H, dd, *J* 10.0, 7.0 Hz, H-7), 4.98 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-5), 4.72 (1H, m, H-13), 4.28 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, H-20), 3.95 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, H-20), 3.76 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-3), 2.21, 2.18, 2.01 (3H each, s, 3 × OAc), 1.92 (3H, s, Me-18), 1.72 (3H, s, Me-19), 1.10 (3H, s, Me-17), 1.02 (3H, s, Me-16); FABMS *m/z* 671 (M + H)⁺ (Found: C, 62.51; H, 6.34; C₃₃H₄₀O₁₂ requires: C, 62.69; H, 6.27%).

7-Acetyl-baccatin-III (**11**; 100 mg) was similarly treated with CF₃COOH (0.1 ml) to yield **13** (44 mg) together with

unreacted **11** (18 mg). Here also some minor products could not be purified.

Compound 13 : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 8.03–8.01 (2H, m, ArH), 7.62–7.45 (3H, m, ArH), 6.25 (1H, s, H-10), 5.71 (1H, m, H-13), 5.56 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, H-2), 5.53 (1H, dd, J 10.0, 8.0 Hz, H-7), 4.95 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-5), 4.29 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, H-20), 3.94 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, H-20), 3.74 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, H-3), 2.25, 2.20, 2.18, 2.04 (3H each, s, 4 \times OAc), 1.95 (3H, s, Me-18), 1.73 (3H, s, Me-19), 1.09 (3H, s, Me-17), 1.03 (3H, s, Me-16); FABMS m/z 629 ($\text{M} + \text{H}$) $^+$ (Found : C, 63.18; H, 6.47. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_{12}$ requires : C, 63.05; H, 6.36%).

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